

The Effect of Theatre Window Viewing, Film Trailers and Social Influence on the Decision to Watch Indonesian Film in the Cinema was Moderated by Film Reviews

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to examine and analyze the influence of theater window viewing, film trailers, social influence and film reviews on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. The method used is a quantitative method. The population in this study were respondents who had watched Indonesian films in cinemas at least once and lived in the areas of Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang and Bekasi (Jabodetabek). Determining the number of samples was carried out using a purposive sampling technique and it was determined that there were 100 respondents. The data analysis method used is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) & SmartPLS (Partial Least Square). The results show that theater window viewing has a positive effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in theaters. Film trailers have a positive effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. Social influence has a positive effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. Film reviews have no positive effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas.

Keywords:- Theater Window Viewing, Film Trailers, Social Influence, Film Reviews, Decision To Watch

I. INTRODUCTION

The world of film in Indonesia has developed so rapidly. There have been many films circulating and mushrooming in Indonesia. Western and Hollywood films often grace Indonesian television screens. That doesn't mean that Indonesia doesn't have its own films. Indonesian people certainly have their own interest in films made by Indonesians. These film works are often obtained from true stories or fairy tales packaged in a textbook or novel. Movies can have an impact on human life, because sometimes it seems as if the audience is experiencing the scenes in the film themselves. The messages contained in the film will make an impression on the soul of the audience. There are many reasons why the film is interesting or not to watch, one of which is the language used by the actors, in other words, how the actors communicate. Today, various film genres have

mushroomed in the entertainment world, including horror, action, cartoon and romantic films which are liked by teenagers. Languages that contain elements of seduction will make the audience carried away.

Film is a means of entertainment that has quite high appeal in various genres produced today. Film also has its own classification in society, which ranges from adults to children. Until now, films are still in great demand, as can be seen from the desire to watch films that are currently appearing in cinemas and television. In addition, several film genres can also be used as a means to convey the moral message contained in the core of the film to the audience as well as mere entertainment. Cinema is one of the places where films are distributed which generates income per unit time and is a source of film revenue in the short term (Eliashberg et al., 2006). Successful screening of films in theaters is a key condition for achieving success in all distribution channels (Eliashberg et al., 2006).

The development of film in Indonesia can be said to be quite significant. This can be seen from the number of film titles appearing in cinemas in Indonesia today. Not only in cinemas that present various films of different genres, films are also present on television screens which present different stories and make the Indonesian film world more colorful, not only Hollywood films but also films made by the nation's children. The more films that are produced, the more genres and film themes are offered such as horror, comedy, romantic drama, family drama with educational themes and so on. In addition, the existence of Indonesian films has begun to be recognized by other countries. Like the film "Yuni", which won the Platform Prize award at the 2021 Toronto International Film Festival and represented Indonesia at the 2022 Oscars.

Based on data from Filmindonesia.or.id, it shows that the number of viewers for Indonesian films that have won prestigious world-class awards is not enough to attract audience interest.

Table 1 Data on the Number of Indonesian Film Viewers in 2021

No	Judul Film	Jumlah Penonton
1	Makmum 2	1.762.847
2	Nussa	446.482
3	Yowis Ben 3	418.526
4	Yowis Ben Finale	369.211
5	Tarian Lengger Maut	222.062
6	Teka-teki Tika	173.017
7	Backstage	138.258
8	Kuyang The Movie	126.108
9	Losmen Bu Broto	120.413
10	Yuni	117.160
11	Seperti Dendam, Rindu Harus Dibayar Tuntas	85.004
12	Kadet 1947	84.196
13	Paranoia	76.614
14	Pintu Surga Terakhir	43.078
15	Akhirat: A Love Story	41.524

Source : <https://Filmindonesia.or.id>, 2022

The film "Yuni", winner of an international festival, was only able to attract 117,160 viewers. A very significant difference compared to the film Makmum 2 which was able to attract as many as 1,762,847 viewers. In addition, like the film "Yuni", the film "Like Revenge, Longing Must Be Fully Paid" also won the Golden Leopard at the 2021 Locarno Film Festival, but only attracted the interest of 85,004 viewers.

Table 2 Data on the Number of Indonesian Film Viewers in 2019

No	Judul Film	Jumlah Penonton
1	Dilan 1991	5.253.411
2	Imperfect: Karier, Cinta & Timbangan	2.662.356
3	Dua Garis Biru	2.538.473
4	Danur 3: Sunyaruri	2.416.691
5	Habibie & Ainun 3	2.245.576
6	My Stupid Boss 2	1.876.052
7	Perempuan Tanah Jahanam	1.795.068
8	Kuntilanak 2	1.726.570
9	Keluarga Cemara	1.701.498
10	Gundala: Negeri Ini Butuh Patriot	1.699.433
11	Bumi Manusia	1.316.583
12	Preman Pensiun	1.147.469
13	Orang Kaya Baru	1.118.738
14	Ghost Writer	1.116.676
15	Yowis Ben 2	1.031.856

Source : <https://Filmindonesia.or.id>, 2022

The film Gundala was screened in the Midnight Madness section at the 2019 Toronto International Film Festival. In addition, at the 2019 Indonesian Film Festival, Gundala received 9 nominations and at the 2019 Maya Cup received 10 nominations. However, based on data from

<http://filmindonesia.or.id/>, the Gundala film only attracted 1,699,433 viewers, which was far different from the Dilan 1991 film which managed to attract as many as 5,252,411 viewers.

A film festival is an organized presentation of films held in one or more cinemas or screening venues, usually in one city or region. Increasingly, film festivals are showing some films outdoors. Films shown may be recent and, depending on the focus of the festival, may include domestic and international releases. Some film festivals focus on a specific film genre (eg, film noir) or a specific subject (eg, horror film festivals and fantasy film festivals). A number of film festivals specialize in short films of a set length. Film festivals are usually an annual event.

The researcher then conducted a journal review to obtain variables related to the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. Previous research conducted by 1.) Montajula Suvattanadilok (2021) The results of the analysis show that promotion, social media activity and trailers are significantly related to the decision to watch a film. 2.) Kuo-Ting Yu1, Hsi-Peng Lu, Chih-Yu Chin and Yu-Shiuan Jhou, (2019) The results of this study reveal that there is the influence of WOM, social influence and external rewards in motivating to watch movies. 3.) Dr. Shamily Jaggi and Lekh Raj (2019) The results show that film elements: trailers and starcasts have a very significant relationship to film evaluation and subsequent film evaluations have a significant relationship to the intention to watch a film. 4.) Tefertiller, A.C., Maxwell, L.C., and Morris II, D.L., (2019) The results showed that movie viewing behavior, social sharing behavior and theater window viewing had a significant effect on the decision to watch movies. Then, these variables were formulated by the researchers to be used as a preliminary survey conducted on 30 respondents to look for important variables that consumers choose when deciding to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. Based on journal reviews and the results of a preliminary survey that was conducted on 30 respondents, there were three variables most chosen by respondents, namely film reviews (film reviews) as many as 93.5% of respondents, then respondents who chose the film trailer variable as many as 87.1% of respondents, Respondents who chose the Theater window viewing variable were 87.1% of respondents and respondents who chose the Social influence variable were 87.1%.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Marketing Management

According to Swastha and Handoko (2016) stated that marketing management is analyzing, planning, executing, and supervision of programs aimed at generating exchanges with target market with the intention of achieving company goals. Meanwhile, according to Boyd, Walker and Larroche (2000), marketing is a social process that involves important activities that enable individuals and companies to get what they need and want through exchanges with other parties and to develop exchange relationships.

B. Definition of Film

According to Law Number 33 of 2009 concerning film, film is a work of cultural art in a social institution and mass communication media that is made based on cinematographic principles with or without sound and can be shown. According to Effendy (2003) film is defined as a product of

culture and a means of artistic expression, while the growth and development of films is very dependent on technology and a combination of artistic elements so as to produce quality films.

C. Trailer Concept as a Film Marketing Strategy

With regard to trailers in films, Moriarty (2011) explains that a film trailer is a preview of a film that will be shown soon. As a form of advertising, film trailers have experienced rapid growth because they are supported by advances in digital technology. Movie trailers are targeted at specific targets based on the nature of the film and its rating, such as G (General) or PG (Parental Guidance). A movie trailer consists of a series of selected scenes from an advertised film. This is because the purpose of a movie trailer is to attract attention, so the scene chosen to be displayed is an interesting, funny, or important part of the film.

D. Social Influence

The behavior of a consumer is also influenced by several factors, one of which is social factors. According to Setiadi (2013), Social Influence is a group of people or organizations that can influence a person's behavior. A group of people or organizations that include reference groups, families, as well as the role and social status of consumers. Reference groups have a direct influence (face to face) or indirect influence on a person's attitude and behavior. Social class, sometimes in the form of a caste system where members of different castes, for certain roles can change their caste membership, including in purchasing a product (Amalia, 2011).

E. Theatre Window Viewing

Movies do not only create awareness of a product that is presented (Corniani, 2001). In this context, film exhibitions through cinema networks, delivering messages and specific transfers of the characteristics of the cinema itself are the final way that is felt by the audience. The promise of cinema is to provide immersive experiences that can transport audiences to a different world, giving them the opportunity to live larger-than-life experiences without the distractions of real life. The application of Screen X technology allows the scenes of a film on the cinema screen to offer spectacular views. With this technology, cinemas can offer immersive experiences for audiences. This innovation will not only strengthen the emotional aspect, but also increase the entertainment value (Mehta, 2019).

F. Review Film

Film review is one of the assessments and explanations or reviews about a film. Factors that can influence a person's decision to watch a film are sources of information and film reviews that can be seen and read by viewers, especially for viewers who are looking for information regarding whether or not a film is good or worth watching. Hassan (2017) argues that reviews of box office films make the audience's frequency high to go to the cinema. This is also supported by research (Gavilan et al., 2019) which states that respondents pay enough attention to film critics through the sites they frequently visit about whether the film will meet their expectations.

G. Decision to Watch Movies

Decision to watch movies is a condition when someone decides to buy a ticket. According to Kotler and Keller (2009: 184), purchasing decisions are basic psychological processes that play an important role in understanding how consumers actually make purchasing decisions. The decision to watch can also be interpreted as a purchase decision, which is an act or process of deciding what to watch, where

and when to do it. According to Peter and Olson (2013) in Permadi, et al. (2014: 3), purchasing decisions are processes of integrity that carried out to combine knowledge in order to evaluate two or more alternatives and choose one of them).

H. Research Model

Researchers designed a research model as shown in the following figure:

Fig 1 Research Model

➤ **Hypothesis:**

- **H1:** Theater window viewing has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas
- **H2:** Film trailers have a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas
- **H3:** Social influence has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas
- **H4:** Film reviews have a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas
- **H5:** Film reviews moderate the relationship between theater window viewing and the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas
- **H6:** Film reviews moderate the relationship between film trailers and the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas
- **H7:** Film reviews moderate the relationship between social influence on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used in this study is a causal research design, where the research design is to test hypotheses and to determine the relationship and influence between the independent variables (independent variables) on the dependent variable (the dependent variable). There is a hypothesis testing regarding the relationship between variables that has been formulated by researchers in causal research. Theater window viewing, film trailers, social influence and film reviews in this study act as independent variables that influence the decision to watch which is the dependent variable. The population of this study are respondents who have watched Indonesian films in cinemas. The sample of this research is respondents who have watched Indonesian films in cinemas at least once and live in the areas

of Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang and Bekasi (Jabodetabek). The sample selection of respondents who have watched Indonesian films in cinemas is expected to be able to evaluate them objectively. The number of samples in this study refers to the sample size guidelines according to Hair et al. (2006), in Mulya Yunisya (2015), that the number of research samples whose exact population size is not known, is at least five times the variables or indicators analyzed. The research design has 20 indicators, so the number of samples taken in this study is at least 20 multiplied by 5 so that 100 respondents are obtained. The sampling technique uses non-probability sampling using purposive sampling techniques. Primary data was obtained from a survey using a questionnaire as a data collection tool. The research questionnaire was created using the Google form and distributed online to respondents. Secondary data was obtained from available literature, articles, journals related to the research topic. The data analysis used in this research is Structure Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of the PLS program, which aims to prove whether there is a correlation between the existing independent and dependent variables.

IV. FINDINGS

A. Measurement Evaluation (Outer Model)

The outer model test is carried out to ensure that the measurement (measurement model) used is feasible to be used as a measurement (valid and reliable). This Outer Model analysis is to find out the relationship between latent variables and their indicators, or it can be said that the outer model defines how each indicator relates to its latent variables.

The outer model test results are presented in the following table:

Table 3 Results of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Value Test

Variabel	AVE Value	AVE value limit	Decision
Theatre Window Viewing (X1)	0,651	0,500	Fulfilled
Trailer Film (X2)	0,732	0,500	Fulfilled
Social Influence (X3)	0,626	0,500	Fulfilled
Review Film (Z)	0,685	0,500	Fulfilled
Decision to watch movies (Y)	0,648	0,500	Fulfilled

Source: PLS Output Results (2023)

Table 4 Discriminant Validity Test Results (Fornell-Larckel)

	Mod 1 (X1.Z)	Mod 2 (X2.Z)	Mod 3 (X3.Z)	X1 (Theatre)	X2 (Trailer)	X3 (Social)	Y (Decision)	Z (Review)
Mod 1 (X1*Z)	1,000							
Mod 2 (X2*Z)	0,122	1,000						
Mod 3 (X3*Z)	0,229	0,550	1,000					
X1 (Theatre)	0,149	0,144	0,071	0,807				
X2 (Trailer)	0,184	-0,078	0,131	0,020	0,865			
X3 (Social)	0,091	0,132	-0,184	0,173	0,270	0,791		
Y (Decision)	0,037	-0,140	-0,071	0,304	0,471	0,381	0,805	
Z (Review)	0,179	-0,059	-0,048	0,065	0,572	0,439	0,369	0,827

Source: PLS Output Results (2023)

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the AVE root value of each variable is higher than the correlation value between that variable and the other variables in the model. With this, it can be said that according to the test with the AVE roots, this model has good discriminant validity.

The requirements used to assess reliability are Chronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values must be greater than 0.70 for confirmatory research and a value of 0.60 - 0.70 is still acceptable for exploratory research.

Table 5 Discriminant Validity Test Results (Fornell-Larckel)

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Reliability Limits	Decision
Theatre Window Viewing (X1)	0,866	0,903	0,700	Reliabel
Trailer Film (X2)	0,824	0,891	0,700	Reliabel
Social Influence (X3)	0,802	0,870	0,700	Reliabel
Review Film (Z)	0,846	0,896	0,700	Reliabel
Decision to watch movies (Y)	0,819	0,880	0,700	Reliabel

Source: PLS Output Results (2023)

The test results based on the table above show that the results of composite reliability and Cronbach alpha show satisfactory values, namely the value of each variable above the value of 0.70. This shows the consistency and stability of the instruments used are high. In other words, all the constructs or variables of this study have become fit

measuring instruments, and all the questions used to measure each construct have good reliability.

B. Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

The steps taken to test the structural model, also known as the Inner Model, are as follows:

Table 6 Result of R Square Value

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y (Decision)	0,394	0,348

Source: PLS Output Results (2023)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the R-square value of the viewing decision variable is 0.394. This R-square value means that the variability of the Watching decision construct which can be explained by the construct variability of Theater window viewing, film trailers, social influence, and film reviews is 39.4% while the rest is explained by other variables outside those studied. According to Chin (1998) in Ghozali and Latan (2015: 81), the R2 values are 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19. It can be concluded that the model is strong, moderate, and weak. With this it can be said that the effect is moderate.

C. Hypothesis test

In this hypothesis testing stage, it will be analyzed whether there is a significant effect between the independent variables on the dependent variable. Testing the proposed hypothesis is done by looking at the path coefficients which show the parameter coefficients and the statistical significance value of t. The significance of the estimated parameters can provide information about the relationship between research variables. The limit for rejecting and accepting the proposed hypothesis is using a probability of 0.05.

Table 7 Hypothesis Test based on Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Mod 1 (X1.Z) -> Y (Decision)	-0,088	-0,116	0,124	0,706	0,480
Mod 2 (X2.Z) -> Y (Decision)	-0,152	-0,127	0,118	1,287	0,199
Mod 3 (X3.Z) -> Y (Decision)	0,026	0,033	0,129	0,203	0,839
X1 -> Y (Decision)	0,289	0,331	0,097	2,977	0,003
X2 -> Y (Decision)	0,377	0,347	0,103	3,655	0,000
X3 -> Y (Decision)	0,256	0,247	0,092	2,798	0,005
X4 -> Y (Decision)	0,028	0,035	0,103	0,268	0,789

Source: PLS Output Results (2023)

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the research results, it is known that theater window viewing has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. This is because the value of the t statistic > 1.96 (2.977 > 1.96) or P values < 0.05 (0.003 < 0.05), so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. The positive coefficient value means that theater window viewing has a positive and significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in theaters. This means that the clearer the sound system sound, the more complete the facilities owned by a cinema, the more people decide to watch Indonesian films in theaters. The results of this study support the results of research conducted by Tefertiller, A.C., Maxwell, L.C., and Morris II, D.L., (2019) which shows that the theatrical viewing window has a significant effect on the decision to watch a film. Thus the first hypothesis (H1) which states "theater window viewing has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas" is proven and can be declared accepted.

"Film trailers have a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas" is proven and can be declared accepted.

Based on the research results, it is known that social influence has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. This is because the value of the t statistic > 1.96 (2.798 > 1.96) or P values < 0.05 (0.005 < 0.05), so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. The positive coefficient value means that social influence has a positive and significant effect on the decision to watch a film. This means that the more people have the perception to watch with friends, the more people decide to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. The results of this study support the results of research conducted by Kuo-Ting Yu1, Hsi-Peng Lu, Chih-Yu Chin and Yu-Shiuan Jhou, (2019) which revealed that there is social influence in motivating people to watch movies. Thus the third hypothesis (H3) which states "Social influence has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas" is proven and can be declared accepted.

Based on the research results, it is known that film trailers have a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. This is because the value of the t statistic > 1.96 (3.655 > 1.96) or P values < 0.05 (0.003 < 0.05), so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. The positive coefficient value means that the film trailer has a positive and significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. This means that the more curious the movie trailer is, the more willing people are to watch Indonesian films in theaters. The results of this study support the results of research conducted by Montajula Suvattanadilok (2021) which shows that film trailers are significantly related to the decision to watch a film. Thus the second hypothesis (H2) which states

Based on the research results, it is known that film reviews have no significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. This is because the value of the t statistic < 1.96 (0.268 < 1.96) or P values > 0.05 (0.789 > 0.05), so that Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected. This means that film reviews are not a factor that someone considers in deciding to watch Indonesian films in theaters. The results of this study do not support the research results of Senhui Fu, Qing Yan and Guangchao Charles Feng (2018) which show that film reviews have an effect on viewing decisions. Thus the fourth hypothesis (H4) which states "Film reviews have a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas" is not proven and can be declared not accepted.

Based on the research results, it is known that film reviews do not moderate the relationship between theatrical viewing window and the decision to watch a film. This is because the value of the t statistic < 1.96 ($0.706 < 1.96$) or P values > 0.05 ($0.480 > 0.05$), so that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected. The results of this study do not support the results of the research by Senhui Fu, Qing Yan and Guangchao Charles Feng (2018), which shows that film reviews moderate the decision to watch. Thus the fifth hypothesis (H5) which states "Film reviews moderate the relationship between theatrical viewing windows on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas" is not proven and can be declared not accepted.

Based on the research results, it is known that film reviews do not moderate the relationship between movie trailers and the decision to watch a movie. This is because the t statistic value < 1.96 ($1.287 < 1.96$) or P values > 0.05 ($0.199 > 0.05$), so that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected. The results of this study do not support the results of the research by Senhui Fu, Qing Yan and Guangchao Charles Feng (2018), which shows that film reviews moderate the decision to watch. Thus the sixth hypothesis (H6) which states "Film reviews moderate the relationship between film trailers and the decision to watch Indonesian films" is not proven and can be declared not accepted.

Based on the research results, it is known that film reviews do not moderate the relationship between social influence on the decision to watch Indonesian films in theaters. This is because the value of the t statistic < 1.96 ($0.203 < 1.96$) or P values > 0.05 ($0.839 > 0.05$), so that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected. The results of this study do not support the results of the research by Senhui Fu, Qing Yan and Guangchao Charles Feng (2018), which shows that film reviews moderate the decision to watch. Thus the sixth hypothesis which states "Film reviews moderate the relationship between social influence on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas" is not proven and can be declared not accepted.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of hypothesis testing and research discussion, the research conclusions are as follows:

- Theater window viewing has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in theaters. This means that the clearer the sound system and the more complete the facilities owned by a cinema, the more people decide to watch Indonesian films in theaters.
- Social influence has a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. This means that the more people have the perception to watch with friends, the more people decide to watch Indonesian films in cinemas.
- Film trailers have a significant effect on the decision to watch Indonesian films in cinemas. This means that the more curious the movie trailer is, the more willing people are to watch Indonesian films in theaters.

This study proposes for further research that is interested in discussing the decision to watch movies. If seen from the research results obtained at the R-square value of 39.4% for the decision to watch as the dependent variable. Thus it can be interpreted that for further research it is necessary to re-examine this research model. Future research may also involve other variables not examined in this study, such as Film Catalog Availability, Movie star, Film Quality and Film Spoiler.

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